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**THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN
TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE****Musaeva M.N.**Candidate of Political Sciences,
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Abstract. This article is devoted to the history of teaching "political science" in independent Uzbekistan, the current problems in teaching this subject, and the importance of innovative technologies in solving them. In particular, innovative pedagogical technologies such as case studies, discussions, and business games in the teaching of "political science" are illustrated with specific examples.

Key words: "political science", "theory and practice of building a democratic society in Uzbekistan", "civil society", higher education institutions, Higher Attestation Commission, 23.00.00 - specialty of political sciences, methodology of socio-political sciences, innovative pedagogical technologies, "case-study" technology, graphic organizers, pedagogical annotation, teaching in small groups, etc.

The huge changes taking place in the world political arena directly and indirectly affect the socio-political and economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Greater openness, loyalty to democratic principles, universal and national values and standards, which began in 2017, not only affects the process of democratization in the social life of the republic, but also affects the acceptance of these changes by the world community, thereby shaping the modern image of Uzbekistan.

In order to analyze the above-mentioned reforms, changes and geopolitical processes, students studying in social and humanitarian sciences, in particular, political science, journalism, philosophy, law and other similar fields, must learn the basic concepts of "Political Science" - political system, political regime, civil society, it is relevant to study political leader, political party, party system, geopolitics, "power centers". Academic subjects such as "Political Science", "Geopolitics", "Civil Society" are necessary for students to deeply understand the interests of the people of Uzbekistan, to know the uniqueness of the democratic reforms implemented in the country, to form ideological immunity, and to have a realistic perception of the objective world.

After the independence of our country, in 1992, the Higher Attestation Commission (HAC) under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan established 23.00.00 scientific councils for the purpose of carrying out and activating scientific research in the field of political science. Later, gradually, the subject of "political science" began to be taught in higher educational institutions of the republic, and political science specialists were trained in this field at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent State University (now the National University of Uzbekistan), Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies.

In accordance with the order of the Minister of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 24, 2015 No. 310 "On the optimization of humanities and socio-economic sciences in the system of higher education", the curricula of bachelor's courses of humanities and "Political science. In the process of drawing up working curricula, the subject "Theory and practice of building a democratic society in Uzbekistan" was changed to the subject "Theory and practice of building a democratic society in Uzbekistan" and measures were taken to transfer the educational literature on the subject "Political science" stored in the libraries of information and resource centers from the general fund to the special fund. The following conclusion was given by the government working group as the reason for removing this subject from the curriculum: "This subject has no scientific methodological basis and its subject and object are abstract. Since the theoretical source and roots of the science of "Political Science" originate from the methodology of socio-political sciences in the former Soviet era, today's civil society, the development of a developed democratic society, the formation of the political consciousness, worldview, active citizenship position of young people, the educational and spiritual nature of the science in raising their political culture - does not meet the requirements of increasing educational effectiveness. This situation occurred due to the abstraction of the methodological foundations, object and subject of science in today's life . But in the past years, the subjects "Theory and practice of building a democratic society in Uzbekistan", "Geopolitics", "Civil society" were taught to students.

In 2016, after Sh.M. Mirziyoev was elected as the president, a group of scientists from the field of social and humanitarian sciences made written and oral appeals to the HAC, proposing to include the network of political sciences in the list of specialties of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, taking into account the quality changes in the life of our society and the advanced world experience. those who did. The working group formed by the HAC checked the validity of the proposal of scientists and prepared a conclusion based on the opinions of leading higher and scientific research institutions. The working group emphasized the expediency of including the network of political sciences in the list of specialties of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel. By the decision of the Board of Education of Ukraine No. 238/2 dated April 24, 2017, the branch "Political Sciences" was included in the list of specialties of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel with the number 23.00.00. It would not be wrong to say that this was the first step towards the revival of the science of "political science".

The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 29, 2019 No. PQ-4139 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of training personnel in the field of political science and fundamental and applied research" was adopted. According to him, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness of personnel training in the field of political sciences, conduct comprehensive systematic research in the field of the formation and development of the political foundations of civil society, national statehood, formulate

and implement the internal and external policy of the state in the context of globalization, and deepen socio-political reforms on this basis. In order to develop recommendations and programs, the "Political Science" undergraduate education and the "Applied Political Science" master's education specialty were opened at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy. After this decision, the subject of "political science" began to be taught in a number of higher educational institutions of the republic. The reason for this is that the demands placed on the personnel trained by the higher education institution include their political system, its main elements, political process participants and political institutions; political conflicts, their sources and participants, and methods of resolving political conflicts; it is determined to know new approaches to the formation of a new architecture of regional and global security and to have the skills to analyze political processes.

Based on the current importance of the "Political Science" course, a number of methodological problems arise in its teaching process. They consist of:

1. Limitation of audience hours. During this time, the teacher should give students an idea of the uniqueness of political science as a science, introduce the history of the formation of political views and doctrines, explain the theoretical basis of the main categories of political science, and form the ability of students to analyze political processes. It should be said that the science of "political science" includes civil society, geopolitics, etc.

2. The need to prevent the course from becoming too theoretical. The goal is not only to study the theoretical foundations of this science, but also to form students' skills to analyze and compare political life events in different countries.

3. To choose effective forms and methods of organizing the educational process in order to increase students' political knowledge. For the implementation of these tasks, it is appropriate to use a special method of teaching science, which activates the acceptance of knowledge by students and ensures that it turns them into political behavior skills.

In order to solve the above-mentioned problem, we offer a number of organizational and methodological methods and forms used in the process of teaching "political science" in a higher educational institution.

The limitation of audience training can be justified by matching the main part of the topics of lectures and seminars with each other. This is the basis for the activation of students' independent work. This is achieved through the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in seminar classes. Students actively and curiously participate in solving business games, graphic organizers (organizers), case studies, which are divided into small groups, compared to traditional questions and answers in seminars.

One of the methods successfully used in the teaching of vocational education subjects is to teach groups of students in pairs or small groups. In this method, the main responsibility is placed on the students, they are focused on increasing their activity.

The experience of pedagogues of advanced countries, as well as our country, shows

that thanks to small groups, much stronger relationships are established between students.

Teaching in small groups:

- teaches students to work cooperatively, to activate the cognitive process, to be communicative, approachable, to listen to the opinions of others;
- in the course of joint performance of the assigned task, there is a tendency to discuss the opinions expressed by comrades;
- they learn to clearly formulate questions and justify their answers;
- helps to realize the learner's potential. An opportunity to learn is created by asking those who do not know. It ensures that learners enrich their knowledge through mutual cooperation;
- shy students will have the opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge and skills;
- gifted and talented students can demonstrate their abilities, help others, teach them and learn from them;
- working in small groups, each student learns to feel himself as a part of the group, to show each other's successes .

Active and innovative technologies of teaching are used in conducting political science seminars. In particular, the seminar dedicated to "Political parties" is usually divided into small groups and conducted in the style of a business game. In it, students, divided into small groups, independently "create" parties, develop their programs and regulations, and engage in electoral campaign debates with rival parties. When studying the topic "Political regimes", it is held in the form of a discussion. That is, each group defends a certain political regime, that is, reveals its achievements. The opposing team highlights their shortcomings through question and answer. Teams compete based on clear facts. There is also a panel of experts who evaluates them at the end of the lesson based on how well the teams have been able to describe the political regimes.

Also, working in small groups and solving cases are used in the organization of independent education in political science.

Recently, the "Case-study" method has been successfully used in the practice of education in foreign countries, and today it is becoming more and more popular in the education of the republic. Therefore, the essence of this method (technology) is discussed at the same place.

"Case-study" technology (situational analysis or analysis of problem situations) - 1) to form students' skills to find the most optimal options by analyzing a specific, real problem situation service technology; 2) teaching technique used in describing real situations.

The important characteristics of educational cases are the presentation of a list of literature to the attention of students in relation to solving a problem situation, providing them with methodical instructions, guidelines and, of course, the teacher's presentation of his own option for solving the problem.

Cases (problematic situations) have a structural structure in the sense of:

1. Pedagogical annotation

2. Introduction.
3. Statement of the case (problem).
4. Tasks (or questions) related to solving a case (problem).
5. List of literature for use.
6. Methodological instructions.
7. The process of solving the case (promoting analysis and solution options, checking the acceptability of options).
8. Organizing a presentation on the solution of the case .

Below is an example of a case used in the field of "Political Science".

Completing the case assignment

INTRODUCTION

Through political knowledge, a person's political consciousness and worldview will rise. As President Sh.Mirziyoev noted, "Our main achievement is the ability of our multi-ethnic nation to overcome the difficulties and trials that arise, its modern worldview, political consciousness and social activity are rising, it is not indifferent to the events around us, on the contrary, it lives with a sense of involvement".

It is known that today the world is experiencing global changes. The conditions of post-bipolar development and globalization lead to an increase in the role of international organizations in world politics and appear as "a complex process consisting of the mutual actions and interactions of state structures and international organizations" . In the context of globalization, international political and economic processes affect the state, that is, its foreign and domestic policies.

The events of the beginning of the 21st century, the changes taking place in the world political life and the existing problems require everyone to have a deeper knowledge of politics and to be seriously engaged in it. This is related to the level of political consciousness and political culture of citizens, creates an opportunity to ensure their freedoms and rights in practice, and has a positive effect on the democratization of society.

It is important for students to form systematic scientific knowledge about political reality, the main principles of its existence, norms of political behavior. Political knowledge is of particular importance for training specialists for the state bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is necessary for students to understand the interests of the people of Uzbekistan through the subject of "Political Science", to know the uniqueness of democratic reforms, to form immunity against threats to the country's national security, and to have a realistic perception of the objective world.

In this regard, it is necessary for our students to analyze the political processes taking place in the world - the structure of interstate associations, international organizations or their problems, as well as the impact of political conflicts on our country on the basis of materials in foreign and local mass media, and form skills for determining their perspective.

The case-assignment brought to your attention is one of them. The case is prepared for 3rd-year students, in which it is aimed at developing their observation, logical

thinking, worldview, analysis of political materials in a foreign language, and perspective-setting skills. This, in turn, can help them analyze political processes and prepare information-analytical documents in the future.

The purpose of referring the case is to acquire and strengthen the theoretical knowledge obtained from the lectures in the "International System and International Relations" department, held within the "Political Science" discipline, and to develop the ability to analyze and determine the stability of real international political processes.

In the process of doing the case, students are primarily required to be able to master the material in the foreign languages they are learning, to be aware of international political processes, to have theoretical knowledge in this field, and to have a broad worldview.

As the students familiarize themselves with the case, they will have the opportunity to use the theoretical and practical knowledge they have acquired in the foreign language, information-analytical document preparation, and political science course during the implementation of this case.

While solving this case, you will:

- cognitive processes: thinking, attention, etc. the importance of development;
- you will learn to acquire the skills and abilities to analyze a problem situation individually and in a group and to accept evidence on it.

ASSIGNMENT. Analyzing the situation presented in the foreign languages you are learning below, identifying the problem that arose in it, the reasons that caused it and ways to solve it, and using additional materials, tell the solution and perspective of the problem.

Explanation. Here, the teacher gives media materials on the international community or activities of international organizations, opinions of statesmen. Below, as an example, we refer to an article published in French at www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/fr.

**Case "Prospects of relations between the European Union and the countries of
Central Asia: developing or facing a crisis?"**

Pendant des années, les relations que les pays d'Asie centrale ont entretenues les uns avec les autres ont été généralement médiocres en raison de différends liés aux questions frontalières et au partage des ressources. Néanmoins, la situation a rapidement évolué après le changement de gouvernement en Ouzbékistan en 2016, ouvrant de nouvelles possibilités de coopération régionale. En mars 2018, pour la première fois depuis les années 90, un sommet des dirigeants d'Asie centrale consacré à la coopération régionale s'est tenu à Astana. Un second sommet a eu lieu en novembre 2019 à Tachkent. Les sources d'énergie renouvelables sont un autre sujet prépondérant, compte tenu de l'immense potentiel de coopération régionale et d'investissement en la matière. À cause de la pandémie de COVID-19, l'économie de cette région a connu une forte baisse en 2020; mais l'année 2021 marque le retour de la croissance, qui devrait atteindre 3,9 %.

Tous les pays d'Asie centrale appliquent une politique étrangère multivectorielle, recherchant un équilibre dans leurs relations avec la Russie, la Chine, l'Union européenne et les États-Unis en particulier. Les relations avec la Turquie et l'Iran sont également importantes. Le Turkménistan demeure largement fermé au monde extérieur et sa «neutralité permanente» a même été reconnue par les Nations unies. Le commerce de l'Union est florissant avec le Kazakhstan, essentiellement dans le secteur des ressources minérales, et les échanges avec l'Ouzbékistan progressent, notamment depuis l'adoption du protocole UE-Ouzbékistan relatif au textile approuvé par le Parlement européen en 2016. L'Union a également salué l'adhésion du Kirghizstan, du Tadjikistan et du Kazakhstan à l'Organisation mondiale du commerce (OMC). Le Kazakhstan et le Kirghizstan sont membres de l'Union économique eurasiatique. En 2016, le Parlement européen a apporté son soutien à la stratégie de l'Union pour l'Asie centrale, tout en formulant le souhait qu'elle soit plus ciblée. La stratégie de l'Union pour l'Asie centrale a été approuvée par le Conseil en juin 2019. Les relations entretenues avec l'Union dans le cadre de cette stratégie dépendent de la volonté des différents pays d'Asie centrale d'entreprendre des réformes et de renforcer la démocratie, les Droits de l'homme, l'état de droit et l'indépendance du pouvoir judiciaire, ainsi que de moderniser et de diversifier l'économie, notamment en soutenant le secteur privé, et les PME en particulier, dans le cadre d'une économie de marché libre. L'importance de l'approche et de la coopération régionales a également été mise en avant lors des réunions ministérielles UE-Asie centrale, dont la seizième s'est tenue le 17 novembre 2020. Les participants ont réaffirmé leur engagement vis-à-vis de la stratégie 2019 pour l'Asie centrale et ont débattu des répercussions de la pandémie de COVID-19 dans la région. En juillet 2020, l'Union européenne, en coopération avec l'Organisation mondiale de la santé (OMS), a annoncé le lancement d'un programme de réaction à la crise de la COVID-19 en Asie centrale, doté d'une enveloppe de 3 millions d'euros en soutien aux pays de la région. Ce programme de solidarité vise à renforcer la résilience à long terme des systèmes de santé nationaux. Les activités du Parlement avec l'Asie centrale sont principalement menées par la commission des affaires étrangères (AFET), la commission du commerce international (INTA), la sous-commission «sécurité et défense» (SEDE), la sous-commission «Droits de l'homme» (DROI) et la délégation pour les relations avec l'Asie centrale (DCAS), ainsi que par l'intermédiaire des commissions parlementaires de coopération (CCP) et de la délégation pour les relations avec l'Afghanistan (D-AF), entre autres. Les CCP avec la plupart des pays d'Asie centrale se réunissent chaque année. Les députés au Parlement européen surveillent la mise en œuvre des accords et se penchent sur les questions relatives aux Droits de l'homme, à la situation politique, à la coopération économique et à la coopération au développement, ainsi que sur les processus électoraux. Un dialogue politique et de sécurité de haut niveau UE-Asie centrale donne lieu à des réunions à intervalles réguliers depuis 2013.

Un dialogue politique et de sécurité de haut niveau a été organisé le 28 mai 2019 à Bruxelles avec les pays d'Asie centrale et l'Afghanistan. Ce dialogue a donné lieu à des discussions sur la stratégie de l'Union pour l'Asie centrale et l'action en faveur de la connectivité UE-Asie. Depuis l'ouverture de la délégation au Turkménistan en juillet 2019, l'Union dispose de délégations dans tous les pays d'Asie centrale. La délégation de l'Union en Mongolie a ouvert ses portes en 2017. Dans le cadre de l'instrument de financement de la coopération au développement (ICD), les pays d'Asie centrale ont reçu des financements à hauteur de 1,02 milliard d'euros pour la période 2014-2020, comprenant à la fois l'aide bilatérale et les programmes régionaux (360 millions d'euros). Horizon Europe est le nouveau programme clé de financement de l'Union pour la recherche et l'innovation. Il est doté d'un budget de 95,5 milliards d'euros, à répartir dans le monde entier sur une période de sept ans (2021-2027). En 2020, le volume des échanges de marchandises se montait à 22,3 milliards d'euros, avec un excédent commercial de 4,1 milliards d'euros en faveur de l'Asie centrale. L'aide porte en priorité sur l'éducation, la sécurité régionale, la gestion durable des ressources naturelles et le développement socio-économique. Le Kazakhstan et le Turkménistan ne peuvent plus prétendre aux volets bilatéraux de l'ICD depuis qu'ils sont entrés dans la catégorie des pays à revenu intermédiaire de la tranche supérieure, mais ils continuent d'avoir accès aux programmes régionaux. L'instrument européen pour la démocratie et les Droits de l'homme (IEDDH) opère dans tous les États, à l'exception du Turkménistan, où les organisations de la société civile sont peu nombreuses, mal organisées et strictement surveillées. L'Union a actualisé les anciens accords de partenariat et de coopération (APC) conclus avec ses partenaires d'Asie centrale. La dixième réunion du groupe de travail UE-Asie centrale sur l'environnement et le changement climatique (WGECC) s'est tenue les 4 et 5 octobre 2021. Le forum de la société civile UE-Asie centrale a eu lieu à Almaty le 6 octobre 2021. Il était principalement consacré au thème «Construire un avenir meilleur: s'engager pour une reprise durable après la COVID-19».

Instructions for solving the case individually.

1. First, meet Keys. Read the case 2 times. Identify the main problem raised in the article.

2. To determine the perspective of the problem raised in the article, first of all, collect and analyze information about the indicated international organization, its structure, activities in your additional native language or other languages from such electronic resources as: <http://www.touteurope.eu>, www.europarl.europa.eu, <http://inosmi.ru>.

3. When you read the case text and additional information, put the following symbols in the margins:

"E" - evidence confirming the problem;

"C" is the cause of the problem;

"M S" - methods of solving the problem recommended by the author.

4. Separate from the article the factors affecting the normal functioning of the international organization. List them.

5. Specify the reasons for the above problem.

6. Identify ways to solve the problem by the author of the article.

7. Analyze the collected data.

8. Based on the results of the analysis, give your opinion on defining the perspective of the international organization.

9. Based on your comments, explain how the perspectives of the European Union and Central Asian countries will affect the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Instructions for solving the case in groups

1. Choose a group leader.

2. Get acquainted with the individual solutions of the case and discuss them.

3. Develop a group solution option for the case. Draw a problem analysis and solution chart on Whatman paper. In the process of filling in columns 1-3 of the table, one group member writes, and the rest speak.

Problem analysis and solution chart

Evidence of the problem	Cause of the problem	Suggested solution by the author	Group solution

4. Using brainstorming, make a list of methods and tools for solving the problem proposed by the group members.

5. Evaluate the ideas for solving the problem as a team and choose the ones you think are the best. Write the selected ideas in the 4 columns of the table.

6. Discuss and determine who will present the results of the group work: the group leader or the entire group members?

7. Evaluate the other group's presentations using the evaluation criteria and indicators below.

Assessment criteria and indicators for group work on the case

Groups	Activity list of group members max. 1	Visual presentation of information max. 1	Clarity, lucidity of oral presentation max. 1.5	Completeness of methods and tools for solving the proposed problem max. 1.5	Total max. 5 (excellent)

Duration: group work - 20 minutes, presentation - 10 minutes.

In conclusion, it should be said that the use of interactive and innovative technologies such as dividing into small groups, business games, press conferences, graphic organizers, and solving cases in the seminar and independent education sessions held within the "Political Science" discipline arouses interest in the science among students. At the same time, they develop the skills of analysis, independent thinking and the ability to express their opinion not only in their native language, but also in the foreign language they are learning. This, in turn, creates a basis for the formation of a political and civil position in students.

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